

Supplementary Materials

These are details on the cDNAs expressed from the sequences downstream of the putative promoters of 3'UTRs. There are 6 figures here, showing the BLAST results using those sequences as probes in searching Gene Expression Omnibus database in NCBI website.

Fig.1. Expression of I3'UTR from human C/EBPβ gene 3'UTR.

<a>. Homo sapiens C/EBPβ mRNA 3'UTR (NCBI Reference Sequence: NM_001285879.1; from 1489, Uppercase letters). The typical TATA sequence is shown in bold letters. Italic letters show the sequences used as probe to search GEO.

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1441 gttcaagcag ctgccccgagc ccctgctcgc ctctcctggc cactgctagC GCGGCCCCCG
1501 CGCGCGTCCC CCTGCCGGCC GGGGCTGAGA CTCCGGGGAG CGCCCGCGCC CGCGCCCTCG
1561 CCCCCGCCCC CGGCGGCGCC GGCAAACTT TGGCACTGGG GCACTTGGCA GCGCGGGGAG
1621 CCCGTCGGTA ATTTTAATAT TTTATTATAT ATATATATCT ATATTTTGT CCAAACCAAC
1681 CGCACATGCA GATGGGGCTC CCGCCCGTGG TGTATTAA AGAAGAAACG TCTATGTGTA
1741 CAGATGAATG ATAAACTCTC TGCTTCTCCC TCTGCCCTC TCCAGGGCC GCGGGCGGG
1801 CCGTTTCGA AGTTGATGCA ATCGTTTAA ACATGGCTGA ACGCGTGT ACACGGGACT
1861 GACGCAACCC ACGTGTAAC GTCAGCCGGG CCCTGAGTAA TCGCTAAAG ATGTTCTAC
1921 GGGCTTGTG CTGTTGATGT TTTGTTTTGT TTTGTTTTT GGTCTTTTT TGTATTATAA
1981 AAAATAATCT ATTTCTATGA GAAAAGAGG GTCTGTATAT TTTGGGAATC TTTTCCGTTT
2041 CAAGCATTAA GAACACTTTT AATAAACTT TTTTGGAGAA TGGTTACAAA GCCTTTTGGG
2101 GGCAGTAAAA AAA
    
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. ESTs found from the searching. Query is the segment in a in Italic letters.

Sbjct 1. wu96h01. x1 NCI_CGAP_Kid3 Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:2527921 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AW025406.1|Length: 399.

```

Query 1 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60
      |||
Sbjct 394 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 335

Query 61 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 120
      |||
Sbjct 334 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 275

Query 121 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAACGTGTCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 180
      |||
    
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Sbjct 274 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 215

Query 181 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCttgttgctgttgatgttttgtttgtttgtttt 240
 |||

Sbjct 214 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTT 155

Query 241 tggctcttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 300
 |||

Sbjct 154 TGGTCTTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 95

Query 301 TTTTGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAGAACAACCTTTAATAAACtttttttGAGA 360
 |||

Sbjct 94 TTTTGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAGAACAACCTTTAATAAACTTTTTTTGA 35

Query 361 ATGGTTACAAAGCCTTTTGGGGCAGTaaaaaa 394
 |||

Sbjct 34 ATGGTTACAAAGCCTTTTGGGGCAGTAAAAAA 1

**Sbjct 2. qq35h08.x1 Soares_total_fetus_Nb2HF8_9w Homo sapiens cDNA clone
 IMAGE:1934559 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AI367654.1|Length: 499**

Query 1 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60
 |||

Sbjct 388 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 329

Query 61 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTAAACATGGCTG 120
 |||

Sbjct 328 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGTTCGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTAAACATGGCTG 269

Query 121 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 180
 |||

Sbjct 268 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 209

Query 181 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCttgttgctgttgatgttttgtttgtttgtttt 240
 |||

Sbjct 208 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTT 149

Query 241 tggctcttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 300
 |||

Sbjct 148 TGGTCTTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 89

Query 301 TTTTGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAGAACAACCTTTAATAAACtttttttGAGA 360
 |||

Sbjct 88 TTTTGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAGAACAACCTTTAATAAACTTTTTTTGA 29

```

Query 361 ATGGTTACAAAGCCTTTTGGGGGCAGTa 388
          |||
Sbjct 28  ATGGTTACAAAGCCTTTTGGGGGCAGTA 1

```

**Sbjct 3.th32h07.x1 NCI_CGAP_Pan1 Homo sapiens cDNA clone
IMAGE:2120029 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AI431972.1|Length: 408**

```

Query 1  AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60
          |||
Sbjct 380 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 321

Query 61  CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 120
          |||
Sbjct 320  CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGG-GGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 262

Query 121 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGTGAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 180
          |||
Sbjct 261 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGTGAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 202

Query 181 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTtggttgctgttgatgTTTTgTTTTgTTTTgTTTT 240
          |||
Sbjct 201 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTT 142

Query 241 tggctctTTTTTgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 300
          |||
Sbjct 141 TGGTCTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 82

Query 301 TTTTGGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAGAACACTTTTAATAAACtTTTTTTGAGA 360
          |||
Sbjct 81  TTTTGGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAGAACACTTTTAATAAACTTTTTTTGA 22

Query 361 ATGGTTACAAAGCC 374
          |||
Sbjct 21  ATGGTTACAAAGCC 8

```

**Sbjct 4. BX114154 Soares_testis_NHT Homo sapiens cDNA clone
IMAGp998H081824 ; IMAGE:742711 5', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID:
emb|BX114154.1|Length: 412.**

```

Query 1  AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60
          |||
Sbjct 32  AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 91

```

Query 61 CTC CAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 120
 |||
 Sbjct 92 CTC CAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 151

Query 121 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 180
 |||
 Sbjct 152 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 211

Query 181 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCttgttgctgttgatgttttgtttgtttgtttt 240
 |||
 Sbjct 212 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTT 271

Query 241 tggctcttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 300
 |||
 Sbjct 272 TGGTCTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 331

Query 301 TTTTGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACTTTTAATAAACtttttttGAGA 360
 |||
 Sbjct 332 TTTTGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAATAACACTTTTAATAAACTTTTTTTGA 391

Query 361 ATGGTTACAAA 371
 |||
 Sbjct 392 ATGGTTAAAAA 402

Sbjct 5. zd93h12.s1 Soares_fetal_heart_NbHH19W Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:357095 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|W93515.1|Length: 391.

Query 11 GTCTATGTGTAC-AGATGAATGATAAA-CTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCTCTCCA-GG 67
 |||
 Sbjct 382 GTCTATGTGTACCAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCTCTCCAAGG 323

Query 68 CGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCG-AAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTGAACGCG 126
 |||
 Sbjct 322 CGCNGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTGAACGCG 263

Query 127 TGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTAATCGCT 186
 |||
 Sbjct 262 TGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTAATCGCT 203

Query 187 TAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTtggctgttgatgttttgtttgtttgtttttggctct 246
 |||
 Sbjct 202 TAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTTGGTCT 143

Query 247 ttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATATTTGG 306

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|||||
Sbjct 142 TTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATATTTGG 83

Query 307 GAATCTTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACTTTTAATAAACtttttttGAGAATGGTT 366
|||||
Sbjct 82 GAATCTTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACTTTTAATAAACTTTTTTTGAAGATGGTT 23

Query 367 ACAAAGCCTTTTGGGGCAGTa 388
|||||
Sbjct 22 ACAAAGCCTTTTGGGGCAGTA 1
    
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Sbjct 6. z109a01.s1 Soares_pregnant_uterus_NbHPU Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:501384 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AA135498.1|Length: 384.

```

Query 1 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60
|||||
Sbjct 366 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 307

Query 61 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 120
|||||
Sbjct 306 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 247

Query 121 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGTGAGCCGGGCCTGAGTA 180
|||||
Sbjct 246 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGTGAGCCGGGCCTGAGTA 187

Query 181 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTtggttgctggtgatgtttgtttgtttgtttt 240
|||||
Sbjct 186 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTT-CTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTT 128

Query 241 tggtc-ttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 299
|||||
Sbjct 127 TGGTCTTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 68

Query 300 ATTTTGGGAATCTTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACTTTTAATAAACtttttttGAG 359
|||||
Sbjct 67 ATTTTGGGAATCTTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACTTTTAATAAACTTTTTTGAG 8

Query 360 AATGGTT 366
|||||
Sbjct 7 AATGGTT 1
    
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Sbjct 247  |||
GAACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGT 188

Query 180  AATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCCCTACGGGCTtggttgctggtgatgttttgtttgtttgttt 239
|||

Sbjct 187  AATCGCTTAAAGATGGTTCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTTGATGTTTGTGTTTGTGTTT 128

Query 240  ttggtccttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 299
|||

Sbjct 127  TTGGTCTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 68

Query 300  ATTTTGGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACTTTTAATAAACtttttttGAG 359
|||

Sbjct 67  ATTTTGGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACTTTTAATAAACTTTTTTTGA 8

Query 360  AATGGTT 366
|||

Sbjct 7  AATGGTT 1
    
```

**Sbjct 9. zc20h05.r1 Soares_senescent_fibroblasts_NbHSF Homo sapiens cDNA clone
IMAGE:322905 5', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|W39546.1|Length: 402.**

```

Query 1  AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60
|||

Sbjct 35  AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 94

Query 61  CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCCGGT-TTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCT 119
|||

Sbjct 95  CTCCAGGCGCCGGC-GNGCGCCGCTCTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCT 153

Query 120  GAACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGT 179
|||

Sbjct 154  GAACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGT 213

Query 180  AATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCCCTACGGGCTtggttgctggtgatgttttgtttgtttgttt 239
|||

Sbjct 214  AATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCCCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTTGATGTTTGTGTTTGTGTTT 273

Query 240  ttggtccttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 299
|||

Sbjct 274  TTGGTCTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 333

Query 300  ATTTT-GGGAATCTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACTTTTAATAAACtttttttGA 358
|||
    
```

Sbjct 334 ATTTTCGGGAATCTTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAGAACAACCTTTTAATAAACTTTTTTTTGA 393

Query 359 GAATGGTTA 367

|||||||

Sbjct 394 GAATGGTTA 402

Sbjct 10. zu63h04.r1 Soares_testis_NHT Homo sapiens cDNA clone

IMAGE:742711 5', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AA401413.1|Length: 350.

Query 1 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60

|||

Sbjct 32 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 91

Query 61 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGT-TTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCT 119

|||

Sbjct 92 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTGTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCT 151

Query 120 GAACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGTGAGCCGGGCCCTGAGT 179

|||

Sbjct 152 GAACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGTGAGCCGGGCCCTGAGT 211

Query 180 AATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTtgttgctgttgatgtttgtttgtttgtttt 239

|||

Sbjct 212 AATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTTGATGTTTGTGTTTGTGTTT 271

Query 240 ttggctcttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 299

|||

Sbjct 272 TTGGTCTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 331

Query 300 ATTTTGGGAATCTTTTCCG 318

|||||||

Sbjct 332 ATTTTGGGAATCTTTTCCG 350

Sbjct 11.AL564683 Homo sapiens FETAL LIVER Homo sapiens cDNA clone

CS0DM007YK12 3-PRIME, mRNA sequence. Sequence ID:

emb|AL564683.3|Length: 938.

Query 1 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60

|||

Sbjct 346 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 287

Query 61 CTCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 120

|||

Sbjct 286 CBCCAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCTG 227

```

Query 121 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 180
          |||
Sbjct 226 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 167

Query 181 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCCCTACGGGCTtggttgctggtgatgttttgtttgtttgtttt 240
          |||
Sbjct 166 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCCAACGGGCTGTTGCTGTTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTGTTTT 107

Query 241 tggctcttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTATA 300
          |||
Sbjct 106 TGGTCTTTTTTTGTATTAWAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGRCGTMATATA 47

Query 301 TTTTGGGAATCTTTTCCGTTTCAAGCATTAAAGAACACTTTTAATAA 346
          |||
Sbjct 46 TTTTRARAATMTTNTNNGTTTAAAGCATTAAAGAACAMNHWTHATAA 1
    
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**Sbjct 12. nl76e09.s1 NCI_CGAP_Br2 Homo sapiens cDNA clone
IMAGE:1056616 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AA557306.1|Length: 323.**

```

Query 1 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 60
        |||
Sbjct 310 AAGAAGAAACGTCTATGTGTACAGATGAATGATAAACTCTCTGCTTCTCCCTCTGCCCT 251

Query 61 CTC-CAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCT 119
        |||
Sbjct 250 CCCACAGGCGCCGGCGGGCGGGCCGGTTTCGAAGTTGATGCAATCGGTTTAAACATGGCT 191

Query 120 GAACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGT 179
          |||
Sbjct 190 GAACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGT 131

Query 180 AATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCCCTACGGGCTtggttgctggtgatgttttgtttgtttgtttt 239
          |||
Sbjct 130 AATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCCCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTGTTTT 71

Query 240 ttggtcttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 299
          |||
Sbjct 70 TGGTCTTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAAGAGGCGTCTGTAT 11

Query 300 ATTTTGGGAA 309
          |||
Sbjct 10 ATTTTGGGAA 1
    
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Query 121 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 180
          |||
Sbjct 169 AACGCGTGTGTACACGGGACTGACGCAACCCACGTGTAAGTGCAGCCGGGCCCTGAGTA 110

Query 181 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCttgttgctggtgatgttttgtttgtttgtttt 240
          |||
Sbjct 109 ATCGCTTAAAGATGTTCTACGGGCTTGTGCTGTGATGTTTTGTTTTGTTTT 50

Query 241 tggctcttttttgTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAA 286
          |||
Sbjct 49 TGGTCTTTTTTGTATTATAAAAAATAATCTATTTCTATGAGAAAA 4
    
```

Fig.2. Expression of I3'UTR from the α -tropomyosin gene 3'UTR.

<a>. Human α -tropomyosin mRNA (3' end). GenBank: AJ000147. 1. No typical TATA box is found. Uppercase letters are the probe (Query) in searching GEO.

```

CDS          <1..147
1 aatcgggctg agtttgcgga gaggtcagta actaaattgg agaaaagcat tgatgactta
61 gaagagaaag tggctcatgc caaagaagaa aacctagta tgcacagat gctggatcag
121 actttactgg agttaaaca catgtgaaaa cctccttagc tgcgaccaca ttctttcget
181 ttgttttggt ttgttttaa cacctgctta ccccttaa at gcaatttatt tacttttacc
241 actgncacag aancatccac aagataccag ctaggtcagg ggggtgggaa atcacataca
301 aaangcaag cccatgtcag ggngatccg gttcaaattg tgccatttcc cgggttgat
361 gcttgccaca cttggtggag gaggtttagc aacacagngt gcttagtgga atcctCACTA
421 AAGCAGGAGA AGTTCCATTC AAAGTGCCAA TGATAGAGTC AACAAGGAAG GTTAATGTTG
481 GAAACACAAT CAGGTGTGGA TTGGTGCTAC TTTGAACAAA AGGTCCCCCT GTGGTCTTTT
541 GTTCAACATT GTACAATGTA GAACTCTGTC CACCACTAAG TTATTTTGTC TTGAGNTTTA
601 CTACAAGATG AGACTATGGA NCCCGCATGC CTGAATTCAC TAAAGCCCCA GGGTCTGTAA
661 GCCACGCTGC TCTTCCGAGA CTTCCATTCC TTTCTGATTG GCACACGTGC AGTCATGAC
721 AATCTGTAGG ATAACAATCA GTGTGATTTC CACTCTTTTC AGTCCTTCAT GTTAAAGATT
781 TAGACACCAC ATACAACCTGG TAAAGGACGT TTTCTTGAGA GTTTTAACTA TATGTAAACA
    
```

. EST and probe in searching GEO. Sbjct: HSFIMI010 Stratagene cat#937212 (1992) Homo sapiens cDNA clone FIMI010 3-, mRNA sequence. GenBank: F13809.1.

```

Query 638 CACTAAAGCCCCAGGGTCTGTAAGCCACGCTGCTCTTCCGAGACTTCCATTCCTTTCTGA 697
          |||
Sbjct 269 CACTAAAGCC--AAGGTCTGTAAGC-ACGCTGCTCTTCCGAGACTTCCATTCCTT-CTGA 214
    
```

```

Query 698 TTGGCACACGTGCAGCTCATGACAATCTGTAGGATAACAATCAGTGTG-ATTTCCACTCT 756
      ||| |||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||
Sbjct 213 TTGCGACACGTGCAGCTCATGACAATCTGTAGGATAACAATCAGTGTGGATTTCCTACTCT 154

Query 757 TTTCAGTCC-TTCATGTAAAGATTTAGACA--CCAC-ATACAA--CTGG-TAAAGGAC- 808
      ||||||||| ||||||||||||||||||| |||| |||| | |||| ||||||||
Sbjct 153 TTTCAGTCCCTTCATGTAAAGATTTAGACCACCCACCATAACCAACCTGGGTAAAGGACC 94

Query 809 -GTTTTTCT--TTG--AG--AGTTTAACTATATGTAAACATTGTATAATGATATGGAATAA 861
      ||||||| ||| || |||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||
Sbjct 93  GTTTTTCTTTGGAAGGAAGTTTAACTATATGTAAACATTGTATAATGATATGGAATAA 34

Query 862 AATGCACATTGTAGGACATTTTCT 885
      ||||||||| ||||||||||||
Sbjct 33  AATGCACATTTTAGGACATTTTCT 10
    
```

Fig.3. Expression of I3'UTR from rat mel-18 gene 3'UTR.

<a>. Rat mel-18 mRNA 3'UTR (N56 cDNA) shown in Fig.6 of reference [30].

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Rat      CTTAACTTGAGGAAAGGGACCCTCTCCTTCC--GCAGCCATCCTTTCCCTCCTTTTACTTTTT
N56      ***
Mouse   CCCCCCTTGAGGAAAGGGACCCTCTCCTTCC--GCAGCCAT-CTTTCCCTCCTTTTACTTTTT
mel-18  1430   *** 1440   1450   1460   1470   1480   1490
Human   CTTAACTTGAGGCCAGGGACCCTCTCCTTCTTCCAGCCAAGCCTCTCCACTCCTTCCACTTTTT
      1230   *** 1240   1250   1260   1270   1280   1290

Rat      CTGGCCCCCTTTTCCA--C-TTTGACTTTCCTGGTTCCTCCCATCTTCAGAGTGGGAGGTGGGTTTT
Mouse   CTGGGCCCTTTTCCA--CTTTGACTTTCCTGGTTCCTCCCATTTTCAGAGTGGGAGGTGGGTTTT
      1500   1510   1520   1530   1540   1550
Human   CTGGGCCCTTTTTCACATTC-TTCTACTTTCCTCCAGCTCTTCCACCTTGGGGGTGGGGGGCGGGTTTT
      1300   1310   1320   1330   1340   1350   1360

Rat      ATAAATAAATCTATCTATATATATATAAATATATATATGTACAATAGG
Mouse   ATAAATAA----ATCTATATATATATAAATATATATATGTAC-ATAGGAAAAAAA
      1560   1570   1580   1590   1600
Human   ATAAATAAATATATATATATGTACATAGGAAAAACCAATATACATACTTA
      1370   1380   1390   1400   1410
    
```

Fig. 6. Nucleotide sequence of N56 cDNA, and the 3' UTR of mouse and human mel-18. Triple stars indicate the translational termination codon.

. EST found searching GEO using N56 cDNA as probe (Query).

Sbjct: UI-R-CA1-bib-h-01-0-UI.s1 UI-R-CA1 Rattus norvegicus cDNA clone

UI-R-CA1-bib-h-01-0-UI 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|BF404720.1 |Length: 299.

```

Query 1   CTTAACTTGAGGAAAGGGACCCTCTCCTTCCGCAGCCAtccttttccctcctttttactt 60
          |||
Sbjct 165 CTTAACTTGAGGAAAGGGACCCTCTCCTTCCGCAGCCATC-TTTCCCTCCTTTTACTT 107

Query 61   tttctggccccccttt-ccactttgactttccctggttcctcccATCTTCACAGTGGGAG 119
          |||
Sbjct 106 TTTCTGGCCCCCTTTTCCACTTTGACTTTCCCTGGTTCTCCCATCTTCAGAGTGGGAG 47

Query 120  GTGGGTTTATAAATAAATCTACTtatatatataaa 155
          |||
Sbjct 46   GTGGGTTTATAAATAAATCTATCTATATATAAAAA 11
    
```

Fig.4. Expression of I3'UTR from human prohibitin gene 3'UTR.

<a>. Homo sapiens prohibitin (PHB), transcript variant 1, mRNA (3'UTR part)

NCBI Reference Sequence: NM_001281496.1. Uppercase letters show the 3'UTR.

Italics are the segment used for probe (Query) in searching GEO. A TATA box is shown in bold.

```

961 agtgaGGGCC CACCCTGCCT GCACCTCCGC GGGCTGACTG GGCCACAGCC CCGATGATTC
1021 TTAACACAGC CTCCTTCTG CTCCCACCCC AGAAATCACT GTGAAATTTT ATGATTGGCT
1081 TAAAGTGAAG GAAATAAAGG TAAAATCACT TCAGATCTCT AATTAGTCTA TCAAATGAAA
1141 CTCTTTCATT CTTCTCACAT CCATCTACTT TTTTATCCAC CTCCCTACCA AAAATTGCCA
1201 AGTGCCTATG CAAACCAGCT TTAGGTCCCA ATTCGGGGCC TGCTGGAGTT CCGGCCTGGG
1261 CACCAGCATT TGGCAGCACG CAGGCGGGGC AGTATGTGAT GGACTGGGGA GCACAGGTGT
1321 CTGCCTAGAT CCACGTGTGG CCTCCGTCCT GTCAGTGTG GAAGGTTTGC GGATGAGGGC
1381 ATGTGCGGCT GAACTGAGAA GGCAGGCCTC CGTCTTCCCA GCGGTTCTG TGCAGATGCT
1441 GCTGAAGAGA GGTGCCGGGG AGGGGCAGAG AGGAAGTGGT CTGTCTGTTA CCATAAGTCT
1501 GATTCTCTTT AACTGTGTGA CCAGCGGAAA CAGGTGTGTG TGAAGTGGC ACAGATTGAA
1561 GAATCTGCC CTGTTGAGGT GGGTGGGCT GACTGTTGCC CCCAGGGTC CTAACACTTG
1621 GATGGACTTG TATAGTGAGA GAGGAGGCT GGACCGAGAT GTGAGTCTG TTGAAGACTT
1681 CCTCTCTACC CCCACCTG GTCCTCTCA GATACCAGT GGAATTCAA CTGAAGGAT
1741 TGCATCCTGC TGGGGCTGAA CATGCCTGCC AAAGACGTGT CCGACCTACG TTCCTGGCCC
1801 CCTCGTTCAG AGACTGCCCT TCTCACGGGC TCTATGCCTG CACTGGGAAG GAAACAAATG
1861 TGTATAAACT GCTGTCAATA AATGACACCC AGACCTCCG GCTCAGCCAA AAAAAAAAA
    
```

b. ESTs found in searching GEO.

Sbjct 1. zo74f02.s1 Stratagene pancreas (#937208) Homo sapiens cDNA clone

IMAGE:592635 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AA160305.1|Length: 503.

```

Query 1   CCTCTCTACCCCCACCTTGGTCCCTCTCAGATACCCAGTGGAAATCCAACCTGAAGGAT 60
          |||
Sbjct 222 CCTCTCTACCCCCACCTTGGTCCCTCTCAGATACCCAGTGGAAATCCAACCTGAAGGAT 163
    
```

```

Query 61  TGCATCCTGCTGGGGCTGAACATGCCTGCCAAAGACGTGTCCGACCTACGTTCTGGCCC 120
          |||
Sbjct 162  TGCATCCTGCTGGGGCTGAACATGCCTGCCAAAGACGTGTCCGACCTACGTTCTGGCCC 103

Query 121  CCTCGTTCAGAGACTGCCCTTCTCACGGGCTCTATGCCTGCACTGGGAAGGAAACAAATG 180
          |||
Sbjct 102  CCTCGTTCAGAGACTGCCCTTCTCACGGGCTCTATGCCTGCACTGGGAAGGAAACAAATG 43

Query 181  TGTATAAACTGCTGTC 196
          |||
Sbjct 42  TGTATAAACTGCTGTC 27

```

Sbjct 2. zm29h01.r1 Stratagene pancreas (#937208) Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:527089 5', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AA114276.1|Length: 420.

```

Query 1  CCTCTCTACCCCCACCTTGGTCCCTCTCAGATACCCAGTGGAAATCCAACCTGAAGGAT 60
          |||
Sbjct 203  CCTCTCTACCCCCACCTTGGTCCCTCTCAGATACCCAGTGGAAATCCAACCTGAAGGAT 144

Query 61  TGCATCCTGCTGGGGCTGAACATGCCTGCCAAAGACGTGTCCGACCTACGTTCTGGCCC 120
          |||
Sbjct 143  TGCATCCTGCTGGGGCTGAACATGCCTGCCAAAGACGTGTCCGACCTACGTTCTGGCCC 84

Query 121  CCTCGTTCAGAGACTGCCCTTCTCACGGGCTCTATGCCTGCACTGGGAAGGAAACAAATG 180
          |||
Sbjct 83  CCTCGTTCAGAGACTGCCCTTCTCACGGGCTCTATGCCTGCACTGGGAAGGAAACAAATG 24

Query 181  TGTATAAACTGCTGTC 196
          |||
Sbjct 23  TGTATAAACTGCTGTC 8

```

Sbjct 3. yh05h08.s1 Soares infant brain 1NIB Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:42313 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|R60946.1|Length: 237.

```

Query 1  CCTCTCTACCCCCACCTTGGTCCCTCTCAGATACCCAGTGGAAATCCAACCTGAAGGAT 60
          |||
Sbjct 234  CCTCTCTACCCCCACCTTGGTCCCTCTCAGATACCCAGTGGAAATCCAACCTGAAGGAT 175

Query 61  TGCATCCTGCTGGGGCTGAACATGCCTGCCAAAGACGTGTCCGACCTACGTTCTGGCCC 120
          |||
Sbjct 174  TGCATCCTGCTGGGGCTGAACATGCCTGCCAAAGACGTGTCCGACCTACGTTCTGGCCC 115

Query 121  CCTCGTTCAGAGACTGCCCTTCTCACGGGCTCTATGCCTGCACTGGGAAGGAAACAAATG 180
          |||
Sbjct 114  CCTCGTTCAGAGACTGCCCTTCTCACGGGCTCTATGCCTGCACTGGGAAGGAAACAAATG 55

Query 181  TGTATAAACTGCTGTC 196
          |||
Sbjct 54  TGTATAAACTGCTGTC 39

```

Sbjct 4. yd92b03.s1 Soares fetal liver spleen 1NFLS Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:115661 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|T80625.1|Length: 346.


```

Query 181 TGTATAAACTGCTGTC 196
          ||| ||| ||| |||
Sbjct 28  TGTATAGACGGCTGTC 13

```

Fig.5. Expression of I3'UTR from mouse ribonucleotide reductase R1 subunit gene 3'UTR.

<a>. 3'region of *M.musculus* gene for ribonucleotide reductase R1 subunit. Uppercase letters show a 446 nt segment in the 3'UTR of R1 gene with tumor suppression activity [32] (GenBank: X72306.1, nucleotide 2619-3064) , and it was used as probe (Query) for searching GEO. A typical TATA box (TATAAAA) in the segment is shown in bold. Note that the sequence in the Query that is homologous with the Sbjct 1 starts from 81st nucleotide downstream of the typical TATA box (2741 nt in the figure<a>), and the Query homologous with the Sbjct 2 starts from 34th nucleotide downstream (2695 nt in the figure <a>). These sequences are in italic.

```

2461 ccatctgggt cctgccccgt tttgtctctc gttagaaaac aaacaggctt
ccaaggaag
2521 aaaagaaaa agaaaaaaaa aaaaaagaa agaaaactag cacatcagtg
ttgaacagaa
2581 ccaacagaag gacagaatgc atgagaagga acaagaatCA GAGATACACT
TGTTCGCACA
2641 CTCAGGCGAA CACTTATAAAA TCCATAAAA AACACTAGTA AACTGGAAGG
CAGGCAGGCC
2701 CTGGGCATGC TGCCTTAGTC TCAAGAGTTT ATAAGAGCAT AGAGGGCCTT
GATTCTTCGG
2761 TGTCCCTCCAT CCCCTAGGT TCTTACTCTC TTTCTTCCTC CTTTTCTATG
GGGCCCCCTG
2821 AGTCATTTGG GGAGGGATTT GATGGAGAAG TCCCTTAGGA CTGAGTATTC
GCAGATGTCT
2881 TGGTCTCTGC ATAATGTCTG GCTGTTTTCA CGTATTAACG TGGCGACGAC
TATCTTATTG
2941 CTGATCCTAT CTCTACTACC ATCCACAAAA CTGTAAAAGC AAATGGACTG
TGGGCCTTCA
3001 TAAGAGTTTC ACAGTACCCC TATTTCTGTA AGGCTGAAAT TCAAACACCT
TTGGTCTAGC
3061 CCCActcttt aactgaggag tgtagaccta cgagccccgg gcttcctatc
tgcttcttat
3121 tttcggggtg taggcttttag tgcaaaccag aacaaaatct tgggtgttcc
ataatgtcca
3181 taatgtaaaa tagcaaaaaa aaaaaaaaa agtcagaggg gtagggaagg
gggaagggag
3241 gaggaagaag gaaaaaggaa aaaggtgttc tggatatctg gttggttact
ttttgttat

```

```

3301 gaaataaaaa tactcgggag atttgcttgc ccacacccaa tatggcggca
    ggagaactcg
3361 ttcccgccag gtccgctttc acccaatgtg gtggaaagga ggcagctctc
    ccgggctttg
3421 cccacactca atatggcggc caagggactc gtgtgctggt tgtctactgc
    tcagtttccg
3481 ccattcaac tcccggcggt gaaacgtcaa gaacgtcatt cg
    
```

** ESTs found from searching GEO.**

Sbjct 1: mai79c09.y1 McCarrey Eddy round spermatid Mus musculus cDNA clone IMAGE: 6447832.5', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|CB273454.1|Length:501.

```

Query 123 AGAGGGCCTTGATTCTTCGGTGTCTCCATCCCCCTAGGTTCTTACACTCTTCTTCCTC 182
          ||| ||||||||| | ||||||||| ||| | ||| ||||||||| |||
Sbjct 66  AGAAGGCCTTGATTGCTTGGTGTCTCCAT-TTCCTCAGCTCTCACACTCTTCTGCCTC 8

Query 183 CTTTTC 188
          || |||
Sbjct 7   CTCTTC 2
    
```

Sbjct 2:Mus musculus adult retina cDNA, RIKEN full-length enriched library, clone:A930005K15 product:unclassifiable, full insert sequence Sequence ID: dbj|AK044286.1|Length: 1973.

```

Query 77  CAGGCCCTGGGCATGCTGCCTTAGTC-TCAAGAGTTATAAGAG---CATAGAGGCCTT 132
          ||||||||| ||||||||| |||| | ||||| ||| | | | || | ||
Sbjct 84  CAGGCCCTGTGCATGCTGCCTCAGTCTTTGAGAGTTCATATGTGTGCCCTTGA---CGTT 28

Query 133 GATTCTTCGGTGTCTCCATCCCC 156
          ||||||| ||||||||| |||||
Sbjct 27  GATTCTT-GGTGTCTCTATCCCC 5
    
```

Fig.6. Expression of I3'UTR from 3'UTR of HP8, a novel C/EBP family gene (i.e. transcription variant 1 of C/EBPα)..

<a>. The 3'UTR of the HP8[31]. 3 TATA sequences are in bold. The letters in italics, downstream of the first TATA sequence, are used as probe (Query) to search GEO.

5'-GCGTGAGGCGCGGCTGTGGGACCGCCCTGGGCCCTCCGGCGGGGACCCAGGGAGTG
GTTTGGGGTCGCCGATCTCGAGGCTTGCCCGAGCCGTGCGAGCCAGGACTAGGAGAT

TCCGGTGCCTCCTAGAAGCCTGGCCTCGTCCGCGTGTCCCCTCCCTTCTCTGAGCCGG
 ACTTGGTGCCTCTAAAGATGAGGGGGCCAGGCGGTGGCTTCTCCCTGCGAGGAGGGGG
 AATTCTTGGGGCTGAGCTGGGAGCCCCGCAACTCTAGTATTTAGGATAACCTTGTGCCT
 TGAAATGCAAACCTCACCGCTCCAATGCCTACTGAGTAGGGGGAGCAAATCGTNCCTT
 GTCATTTTATTTGGAGGTTTCTGCCTCCTTCCCAGGCTACAGCAGACCCCATGAGA
 GAAGGAGGGGAGCAGGCCCGTGCAGGAGGAGGGCTCAGGGAGCTGAGATCCCGACAA
 GCCCGCCAGCCCCAGCCGCTCCTCCACGCCTGTCTTAGAAAGGGGTGGAAACATAGG
 GACTTGGGGCTTGGAACTAAGGTTGTTCCCCTAGTTCTACATGAAGGTGGAGGGTCTC
 TAGTTCCACCCCTCTCCACCTCCCTCCGCACACACCCACCCACCCAGCCTGCTATAGGCT
 GGGCTTCCCCTTGGGCGGAACTCACTGCGATGGGGGTCACCAGGTGACAGTGGGACCCC
 CACCCCGAGTCACACCAGAAAGCTAGGTGTGGGTCAGCTCTGAGGATGTATACCCCTGGTG
 GGAGAGGGAAACCTAGAGTCTGGCTGTGGGGCGGGCATGGGGGGTGAAGGGCCACTGGG
 ACCCTCAGCCTTGTGTTGACTGTATGCCTTCAGCATTGCCTAGGAACACGAAGCACGATCAGT
 CCATCCCAGACCGGAGTATGACAAGCTTTCCAAATATTTGCTTATCAGCGATATCAAACTG
 TATCTGCCTCTGTGCCCCAGCAGTGCCTTGTGCAATGTGAATGTGCGTCTCTGCTAACACC
 ATTTATTTGGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTGACTCGCTTGCCAAAATGAGACTCTCCGTCGGC
 AGCGGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCTGGG
 GACCAATGACCTGAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTCCCAGCCCCACCGGCCTGG
 GCTGCCACAAGGCTTGTCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCCGAGGGAGGTGGCCTCC
 CCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGAAGGACGGCTTGGTTCTCTTTTGGGGAGAAC
 GTAGAGTCCACTCTACATGTTTTATGATATTATATCTATAATATAAAC-3'

** ESTs found from searching GEO.**

Sbjet 1. ba82c12. x1 NIH_MGC_21 Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:2906902 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|BE301008.1|Length: 551.

```

Query  183  TCAGCATTGCCTAGGAACACGAAGCACGATCAGTCCATCCCAGA----CCGGAGT-ATGA  237
          |||
Sbjet  551  TCAGCATTGCCTAGGAACACGAAGCACGATCAGTCCATCCCAGAGGGACCGGAGTTATGA  492

Query  238  CAAGCTTTCCAAATATTTTGCTT-ATCAGC-GATATCAAACT-GTATCTG-CCTCTGTG  293
          |||
Sbjet  491  CAAGCTTTCCAAATATTTTGCTTTATCAGCCGATATCAAACTTGTATCTGGCCTCTGTG  432

Query  294  CCCAGCAGTGCCTTGTGCAATGTGAATGTGCG--TCTCTGCTAA-CCACCAttttattt  350
          |||
Sbjet  431  CCCAGCAGTGCCTTGTGCAATGTGAATGTGCGCGTCTCTGCTAAACCACCATTTTATTT  372

Query  351  ggtttt-gttttgttttggttttgACTCG----CTTGCCAAAATGAGACTCTCCGTCGGC  405
          |||
Sbjet  371  GGTTTTTGTTTTGTTTTGGTTTTG-CTCGGATACTTGCCAAAATGAGACTCTCCGTCGGC  313
    
```

Query 406 AGCGGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCTG 465
 ||| ||
 Sbjct 312 AGCTGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCTG 253

Query 466 GGG-ACCAATGACCTGAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTGGCCCTCAGCTTCCCCAGCCCCACCGGC 524
 ||| ||||| ||||| |||
 Sbjct 252 GGGGACCAATGAGGTGAGGGGGTCTCCTTGGCCCTCAGCTTCCCCAGCCCCTCCGGC 193

Query 525 CTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTGTCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGG--AGGGAGGTG 582
 ||| ||||||||
 Sbjct 192 CTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTGTCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGGAAGGGAGGTG 133

Query 583 GCCTCC--CCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCA--GAAGGACGGCTTGGTTCTCTTCTT 638
 ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||||||||||||||||||||
 Sbjct 132 GCCTCCCGCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGGAAGGACGGCTTGGTTCTCTTCTT 73

Query 639 TTGGGGAGAACGTAGAGTC-CACTCTACATGTTTTATGATATTATATCTATAATATAAAC 697
 ||||||||||||||||| ||||| ||||||||| |||||||||||||||||
 Sbjct 72 TTGGGGAGAACGTAGAGTCTCACTCTAGATGTTTTATG-TATTATATCTATAATATAAAC 14

Sbjct 2.wr26a03.x1 NCI_CGAP_Pr28 Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:2488780 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AI971171.1|Length: 515.

Query 225 GACCGGAGT-ATGACAAGCTTTCCAAATATTTTGCTT-ATCAGC-GATATCAACACT-GT 280
 ||||||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||||| ||||||||| ||
 Sbjct 510 GACCGGAGTTATGACAAGCTTTCCAAATATTTTGCTTTATCAGCCGATATCAACACTTGT 451

Query 281 ATCTG-CCTCTGTGCCCCAGCAGTGCCTTGTGCAATGTGAATGTGCG--TCTCTGCTAA- 336
 ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||||||||| |||||||||
 Sbjct 450 ATCTGGCCTCTGTGCCCCAGCAGTGCCTTGTGCAATGTGAATGTGCGCGTCTCTGCTAAA 391

Query 337 CCACCAttttatattggtttt-gttttgttttggttttgACTCG----CTTGCCAAAATGA 391
 ||||||||||||||||| ||||||||||||||||| ||||| |||||||||
 Sbjct 390 CCACCATTTTATTTGGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTG-CTCGGATACTTGCCAAAATGA 332

Query 392 GACTCTCCGTCGGCAGCGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGAT 451
 ||||||||||||||||| ||||||||||||||||| |||||||||||||||||
 Sbjct 331 GACTCTCCGTCGGCAGCTGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGAT 272

Query 452 TACTTTTGATCCTGGGG-ACCAATGACCTGAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTGGCCCTCAGCTTTC 510
 ||||||||||||||||| ||||| ||||| |||||||||||||||||
 Sbjct 271 TACTTTTGATCCTGGGGACCAATGAGGTGAGGGGGTCTCCTTGGCCCTCAGCTTTC 212

Query 511 CCAGCCCCACCGCCTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTGTCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGT 570

```

                |||
Sbjct 211 CCAGCCCCTCCGGCCTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTTGTCCTCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGT 152

Query 571 CGG--AGGGAGGTGGCCTCC--CCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCA--GAAGGACGGC 624
                |||
Sbjct 151 CGGGAAGGGAGGTGGCCTCCCGCCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGGGAAGGACGGC 92

Query 625 TTGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGGGAGAACGTAGAGTC-CACTCTACATGTTTTATGATATTATA 683
                |||
Sbjct 91 TTGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGGGAGAACGTAGAGTCTCACTCTAGATGTTTTATG-TATTATA 33

Query 684 TCTATAATATAAAC 697
                |||
Sbjct 32 TCTATAATATAAAC 19
    
```

Sbjct 3. qt36e11. x1 Soares_pregnant_uterus_NbHPU Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:1950092 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|AI335709.1|Length: 443.

```

Query 287 CTCTGTGCCCCAGCAGTGCCTTGTGCAATGTGAATGTGCG--TCTCTGCTAA-CCACCA 343
                |||
Sbjct 443 CTCTGTGCCCCAGCAGTGCCTTGTGCAATGTGAATGTGCGCGTCTCTGCTAAACCACCAT 384

Query 344 tttatattggtttt-gttttggttttgggtttgACTCG----CTTGCCAAAATGAGACTCTC 398
                |||
Sbjct 383 TTTATTTGGTTTTTGTGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTG-CTCGGATACTTGCCAAAATGAGACTCTC 325

Query 399 CGTCGGCAGCGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTT 458
                |||
Sbjct 324 CGTCGGCAGCTGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTT 265

Query 459 GATCCTGGGG-ACCAATGACCTGAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTCCCAGCCC 517
                |||
Sbjct 264 GATCCTGGGGGACCAATGAGGTGAGGGGGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTCCCAGCCC 205

Query 518 CACCGGCCTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTTGTCCTCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGG--AG 575
                |||
Sbjct 204 CTCCGGCCTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTTGTCCTCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGGGAAG 145

Query 576 GGAGGTGGCCTCC--CCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCA--GAAGGACGGCTTGGTTC 631
                |||
Sbjct 144 GGAGGTGGCCTCCCGCCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGGGAAGGACGGCTTGGTTC 85

Query 632 TCTTCTTTTGGGGAGAACGTAGAGTC-CACTCTACATGTTTTATGATATTATATCTATAA 690
                |||
    
```

Sbjct 84 TCTTCTTTGGGGAGAACGTAGAGTCTCACTCTAGATGTTTTATG-TATTATATCTATAA 26

Query 691 TATAAAC 697
 |||||

Sbjct 25 TATAAAC 19

Sbjct 4. yv27f08.s1 Soares fetal liver spleen 1NFLS Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:243975 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|N39553.1|Length: 503.

Query 233 TATGACAA-GCTTT-CCAAATATTTGCTT-ATCAG--CGATATCAA-CACT-GTATCTG 285
 ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||

Sbjct 502 TATGACAAAGCTTTNCCAAATATTTGCTTTATCAAGCCGATATCAAACACTGTATCTG 443

Query 286 --CCTCTGTGCCCC--AGCAGTGCC-TTGTGC-AATGTGAATGTGCG--TCTCTGCTAA- 336
 ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||

Sbjct 442 GCCCTCTGTGCCCCCAGCAGTGCCCTGTGCCAATGTGAATGTGCGCGTCTCTGCTAAA 383

Query 337 CCACCAttttatattggtttt-gttttggtttggtttgACTCG----CTTGCCAAAATGA 391
 ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||

Sbjct 382 CCACCATTTTATTTGGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTGTTTTG-CTCGGATACTTGCCAAAANGA 324

Query 392 GACTCTCCGTCGGCA-GCGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGA 450
 ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||

Sbjct 323 GACTCTCCGTCGGCAAGCTGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGA 264

Query 451 TTACTTTTGATCCT-GGGGACCAATGACCTGAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTC 509
 ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||

Sbjct 263 TTACTTTTGATCCTGGGGACCAATGAGGTGAGGGGGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTC 204

Query 510 CCCAGCCCCACGGCCTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTTGCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGG 569
 ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||

Sbjct 203 CCCAG-CCCTCCGGCCTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTTGCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGG 145

Query 570 TCGG--AGGGAGGTGGCCTCC--CCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCA--GAAGGACGG 623
 ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||

Sbjct 144 TCGGGAAGGGAGGT-GCCTCCGCCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGGGAAGGACGG 86

Query 624 CTTGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGGGAGAACGTAGAGTC-CACTCTACATGTTTTATGATATTAT 682
 ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||

Sbjct 85 CTTGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGGGAGAACGTAGAGTCTCACTCTAGATGTTTTATG-TATTAT 27

Query 683 ATCTATAATATAAAC 697
 |||||


```

Query 365 ttggttttgACTCG----CTTGCCAAAATGAGACTCTCCGTCGGCAGCGGGGGGAAGGGT 420
      ||||| ||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 355 TTGGTTTTG-CTCGGATACTTGCCAAAATGAGACTCTCCGTCGGCAGCTGGGGGAAGGGT 297

Query 421 CTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCTGGGG-ACCAATGACCT 479
      ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 296 CTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCTGGGGACCAATGAGGT 237

Query 480 GAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTCCCAGCCCACCGGCTGGGCTGCCACAA 539
      ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 236 GAGGGGGTTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTCCCAGCCCCTCCGGCTGGGCTGCCACAA 177

Query 540 GGCTTGTCCTCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGG--AGGGAGGTGGCTCC--CCAACGC 595
      ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 176 GGCTTGTCCTCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGGGAAGGGAGGTGGCTCCCGCCAACGC 117

Query 596 ATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCA--GAAGGACGGCTTGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGGGAGAACGTAG 653
      ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 116 ATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGGAAGGACGGCTTGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGGGAGAACGTAG 57

Query 654 AGTC-CACTTACATGTTTTATGATATTATATCTATAATATAAAC 697
      |||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 56 AGTCTCACTTAGATGTTTTATG-TATTATATCTATAATATAAAC 13
    
```

Sbjct 7. zh64g09. s1 Soares_fetal_liver_spleen_1NFLS_S1 Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:416896 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|W87364.1|Length: 422.

```

Query 303 TGCCTTGCAATGTGAATGT--GCGTCTCTGCTAA-CCACCAtttta-tttggtttt-g 357
      ||||| | ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 422 TGCCTTATNCAATGTGAATGTNCGCTCTCTGCTAAACCACCATTTTAATTTGGTTTTTG 363

Query 358 ttttgt-tttggttttgACTCG----CTTGCC-AAAATGAGACTCTCCGTCGGCAGCG-G 410
      | |||| | ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 362 TNTTGTCTNTGGTTTTG-CTCGGATACTTGCCNAAAATGAGACTCTCCGTCGGCAGCATG 304

Query 411 GGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCT-GGGGA 469
      ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 303 GGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCTGGGGGA 244

Query 470 CCAATGACCTGAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTCCCAGCCCACCGGCTGGG 529
      ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| ||||| |||||
Sbjct 243 CCAATGAGGTGAGGGGGTTCCTTTGCCCTCAGTNTCCCAG-CCNNCCGGCCTGGG 185
    
```

Query 530 CTGCCACAAGGCTTGTCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGG--AGGGAGGTGGCCTC 587
 || | ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||||||| |||||
 Sbjct 184 CTTNCTACAAGGCTTGTCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGGGAAGGGAGGT-GCCTC 126

Query 588 C--CCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCA--GAAGGACGGCTTGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGG 643
 | ||||||||||||||||||||||| |||||||||||||||||||||||
 Sbjct 125 CCGCCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGGAAGGACGGCTTGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGG 66

Query 644 GAGAACGTAGAGTC-CACTCTACATGTTTTATGATATTATATCTATAATATAAAC 697
 ||||||||||||| ||||| ||||||||| |||||||||||||||||||
 Sbjct 65 GAGAACGTAGAGTCTCACTCTAGATGTTTTATG-TATTATATCTATAATATAAAC 12

Sbjct 8. yb29f06.s1 Stratagene fetal spleen (#937205) Homo sapiens cDNA clone IMAGE:72611 3', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|T52003.1|Length: 425.

Query 285 GCCTCTGTGCCCC-AGCAGTGCCTTGTGCAA-TGTGAA-TGT--GCGTCTCTGCTAA-CC 338
 ||||||||||||| | | ||||||| || ||| || ||| ||| ||||||||| ||
 Sbjct 423 GCCTCTGTGCCCCAANAAGGCCTTGTGNAATGTNAAATGTNCGCGNCTCTGCTAAACC 364

Query 339 ACC-Attttatttgg-ttttgtttggttttggtttgACTCG----CTTGCCAAAATGAG 392
 ||| | || | |||| ||||||||||||||||||||||| |||| | |||||||||||||
 Sbjct 363 ACCCANTTAANTTGGNTTTGTTTTGTTTTGGTTTTG-CTCGGANACTTGCCAAAATGAN 305

Query 393 ACTCTCCGTCGGCAGCGGGGGAAGGGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATT 452
 ||||||||||||||||| ||||||||||||||||| |||||||||||||||||||
 Sbjct 304 ACTCTCCGTCGGCAGCTGGGGGAAGGGTCTGANACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATT 245

Query 453 ACTTTTGATCCT-GGGGACCAATGACCTGAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTCCC 511
 ||||||||| ||| ||||||||||||| ||||||||| ||||||||||||||||||| |
 Sbjct 244 ACTTTTGANCTGGGGACCAATGAGGTGAGGGGGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTCTC 185

Query 512 CAGCCCCACCGCCTGGGCTGCCACAAGGCTTGTCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTC 571
 ||| ||| ||||||||||||||||||| ||||||||||||||||||| |||||||||||
 Sbjct 184 CAG-CCCTCCGGCCTGGGCTGCCANAAGGCTTGTCCCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTC 126

Query 572 GG--AGGGAGGTGGCCTCC--CCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCA--GAAGGACGGCT 625
 || ||||||||| ||||| ||||||||||||||||||||||| |||||||||||||
 Sbjct 125 GGAAGGGAGGT-GCCTCCGCCAACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGGAAGGACGGCT 67

Query 626 TGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGGAGAACGTAGAGTC-CAC-TCTACATGTTTTATGATATTATA 683
 ||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||||| ||| ||||| ||||||||||| |||||
 Sbjct 66 TGGTTCTCTCTTTTGGGAGAACGTAGAGTCTCACNTCTAGATGTTTTATG-TATTATA 8

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Query 684 TCTATAA 690
          |||
Sbjct 7   TCTATAA 1

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**Sbjct 9. y143d10.r1 Soares breast 3NbHBst Homo sapiens cDNA clone
IMAGE:161011 5', mRNA sequence. Sequence ID: gb|H25129.1|Length: 357.**

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Query 366  tggttttgACTCG-----CTTGCC-AAAATGAGA-CTCTCCGTCGGCAGCGGGGGAA-G 417
          |||
Sbjct 357  TGGTTTTG-CTCGAAAACTTGCCAAAATGAAACTCTCCGTCGGCAACTGGGGGAAAG 299

Query 418  GGTCTGAGACTCCCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCT--GGGGACCAATG 475
          |||
Sbjct 298  GGTCTGANACTCTCTTTCCTTTTGGTTTTGGGATTACTTTTGATCCCTGGGGACCAATG 239

Query 476  ACCTGAGGGGAGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTT-CCCAGCCCCACCGGCCTGGGCTGCC 534
          |
Sbjct 238  AGGTGAGGGGGTTCTCCTTTGCCCTCAGCTTTANCCAG-CCCTCCGGCCTGGGCTGCC 180

Query 535  CACAAGGCTTGTCCTCCAGAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGG--AGGGAGGTGGCCTCC--CC 590
          ||
Sbjct 179  CANAAGGCTTGTCCTCCANAGGCCCTGGCTCCTGGTCGGGAAGGGAGGT-GCCTCCCGCC 121

Query 591  AACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCA--GAAGGACGGCTGGTTCTCTTCTTTGGGGAGAA 648
          |||
Sbjct 120  AACGCATCACTGGGGCTGGGAGCAGGAAGGACGGCTGGTTCTCTTCTTTGGGGAGAA 61

Query 649  CGTAGAGTC-CACTCTACATGTTTTATGATATTATATCTATAATATAAAC 697
          |||
Sbjct 60   CGTAGAGTCTCACTCTAGATGTTTTATG-TATTATATCTATAATATAAAC 12

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